

Rice response to Cu application

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To evaluate rice response to Cu application, Saket 4 was transplanted in a Gangetic alluvium-Typic Hapludalf, loam, pH 7.3 that was moderately deficient in DTPA extractable Cu (0.47 ppm). Zero, 10, 20, or 40 kg Cu/ha as copper sulfate

and 120 kg N/ha as urea (split applied at 60 + 30 + 30), 60 kg P/ha as superphosphate, and 60 kg K/ha as muriate of potash were applied to all the plots. Plant samples were collected 40 and 80 d after transplanting and grain and straw samples at harvest. Cu content was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Pooled averages of the data presented in the table indicate that applying Cu increased dry matter production at all growth stages. Maximum increase was

recorded with 20 kg Cu/ha. Grain production also increased by 14%.

Cu concentration in the rice plants decreased gradually toward maturity and reached minimum levels in the straw. Cu content of plants and of grains at 80 d were similar. Applying 20 and 40 kg Cu affected Cu content similarly, indicating that the 20 kg application was sufficient for these cropping conditions. Maximum Cu uptake was with 40 kg Cu/ha. □

Effect of Cu application on dry matter production, grain yield, and Cu content and uptake by rice, Varanasi, India.

Cu (kg/ha)	40 d after transplanting			80 d after transplanting			Straw			Grain		
	Dry matter (t/ha)	Cu content (ppm)	Cu uptake (g/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	Cu content (ppm)	Cu uptake (g/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	Cu content (ppm)	Cu uptake (g/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	Cu content (ppm)	Cu uptake (g/ha)
0	0.5	24	13	2.9	11	32	4.4	6	24	2.9	11	31
10	0.6	28	17	3.4	13	44	4.9	7	33	3.2	14	46
20	0.7	34	24	3.8	14	54	5.1	7	37	3.4	15	51
40	0.7	35	24	3.7	14	54	5.2	7	39	3.3	16	51
LSD (0.05)	.02	1.2	0.8	.08	0.4	2.0	.12	0.3	2.0	.06	0.4	1.6

Unicellular mucilaginous blue-green algae (BGA): impressive blooms but deceptive biofertilizers

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Certain mucilaginous N₂-fixing BGA develop impressive blooms in rice fields. Because of their high water and ash content, however, their N contribution may be low. The figure shows a bloom that has been observed annually since 1980 in no-N plots of the IRRI farm in dry season. It comprises *Aphanothece* as dominant genus and *Nostoc* and *Gloeotrichia* as associated genera. Highest fresh weight biomass recorded was 58 t/ha, but 98.6% water and 54% ash contents limited N content to 13 kg/ha.

In 1984 dry season, we studied the effects of such a bloom on rice yield. The experiment was in a Latin square of 16 4 × 4-m plots, with control and BGA treatments. After 2 plowings and harrowings, IR60 was transplanted at 20 × 20-cm spacing. A basal application

BGA bloom comprising *Aphanothece*, *Nostoc*, and *Gloeotrichia* genera.

of 30 kg P/ha, 30 kg K/ha, and 0.5 kg ai furadan/ha was made in all the plots at transplanting. Two days later, half of the plots were inoculated with 20 g/m² of a dry algal inoculum collected from the

same plots in May 1983. At the time of application, the inoculum contained 2.2 × 10⁶ colony-forming units of N₂-fixing BGA per g dry weight. The dominant strains in the inoculum were